

THE ANTHEM OF THE COUNTRY IN THE POEMS OF MUHAMMAD YUSUF, THE FORMATION OF A SENSE OF PATRIOTISM IN YOUNG PEOPLE.

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Аннотация: в данной статье говорится о развитии Родины, вкладе в репутацию нации, самоотверженности, честном труде, воспитании чувств борьбы во славу народа, развитию страны, национальных ценностях.

Annotation: this article talks about the development of the Motherland, contribution to the reputation of the nation, selflessness, honest work, education of feelings of struggle for the glory of the people, development of the country, national values.

Ключевые слова: родина, патриотизм, верность, служение Отечеству, труд.

Key words: homeland, patriotism, loyalty, service to the country, work.

While thinking about the development of the new Uzbekistan, the future strategy, major changes are being made in the education system of the entire republic. Pedagogues and social institutions are designed to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism with the help of information communicative and advanced educational technologies, modularized and modern educational methods provided by these reforms, to improve moral and moral, to form a deep sense of citizenship, to create ideological immunity that protects against alien ideological influences, and to ensure the effectiveness of training. Therefore, it is important to educate young people in the spirit of the national ideal, to develop in them a sense of pride in their country and people, and to be ready to protect it.

Because the policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of education is distinguished by its national character. The educational process organized on the basis of the principle of humanity should ensure the free development of students.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6017 dated June 30, 2020 "On measures to fundamentally reform and advance the state policy regarding youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a new stage" and "Youth of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the organization of the activities of the Agency" Decision No. PQ-4768 of June 30, 2020 after its adoption, extensive positive changes were made in the education system of our country, in particular, the role of social institutions in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism. In

particular, the role of social institutions in the formation of patriotism among young people and teaching students to work independently is considered an urgent issue.

It had an effective impact on the development of all areas of the economic and spiritual development of New Uzbekistan. At the same time, he set huge responsibility tasks for literature and writers. The fact that the growing young generation lives as my people, my country, and is brought up in the spirit of confidence in the prosperity of our country depends to a large extent on the educational process. According to the laws and decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of education, it is necessary to choose and organize the content and management of education in accordance with national values, historical and spiritual education in order to implement these great works.

It is known that the future of our people, the future development of the country depends on the development of our children. Our ancestors, who were the proud children of the Uzbek people, were able to show their sense of patriotism. Among them, Muhammad Yusuf has a special place, for example his Uzbek poem:

Men dunyoni nima qildim,
O`zing yorug` jahonim.
O`zim xoqon,
O`zim sulton
Sen taxti Sulaymonim.
Yolg`izim, Yagonam deymi,
Toppingan koshonam deymi,
O`zing mening ulug`lardan
Ulug`imsan, Vatanim...
Kim Qashqarni qildi makon,
Kim Enasoy tomonda,
Jaloliddin — Kurdistonda,
Boburing — Hindistonda,
Bu qanday yuz qarolik deb,
Yotarlar zimistonda.
Tarqab ketgan to`qson olti
Urug`imsan, Vatanim...

It is rare to find a countryman who has not heard the song based on this poem by Muhammad Yusuf and has not sung it together with the singer. The composer has found music that is so suitable for the text of the poem - its

essence, that it seems as if the poet has finished the poem by humming this music in advance. The development (dynamism) of the content and tone of the poem begins its second life in music, the singer's voice sometimes increases and sometimes decreases, expressing the stages of historical rise and decline of Uzbek.

In fact, there are countless poems written about the Motherland, mentioning the names of great people in the history of our country one by one, remembering the recent events, and praising them. Q. In almost all of them, Amir Temur, Manguberdi, Navoi and Babur, Cholpan and Fitrat are certainly mentioned, and they are glorified through well-known qualities and similes. However, why none of them became famous like Muhammad Yusuf's poem? Why these poetic lines did not move to the hearts of millions as a living feeling?

So, singing about the Motherland will be different. This poem-song is also sincere, it goes from the heart to the heart and has an effect on the contrary. In Ozod Sharafiddinov's article "I will never leave your arms if I die" dedicated to the feeling of the Motherland in the human heart, the scientist expressed his dismay at those who "patriotize" not in practice, but more in words. Boyagi's poems were also "born" after thoughts such as "It is necessary to write on the theme of the Motherland, if it becomes a wonderful song, if it becomes a more popular song, if the state gives it a title ..." but it can be said that it is the pale ridges that have given life since birth. Because it is impossible to love the Motherland with love and passion, so it is impossible to write and sing about it with the same goals.

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